

Ionization Constant of Ferron in Mixed-Solvents

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The ionization constant of Ferron, 7-iodo 8-hydroxy quinoline 5-sulphonic acid (sodium salt) have been studied by potentiometric method in methanol-water, ethanol-water, isopropanol-water, acetone-water, 1,4-dioxane-water, glycol-water and glycerol-water mixtures at constant ionic strength of 0.1M KNO_3 at 25°, 35° and 45°. The variation of pK_1 with inverse dielectric constant gave a linear relationship from which the mean radii of dianion were calculated in the above solvents. From the variation of pK_1 with temperature ΔH , ΔS , and ΔG values were calculated in iso-composition mixtures. A plot of ΔH versus ΔS gave a straight line from which the isokinetic temperature was calculated as 181°K.

A survey of literature on Ferron, 7-iodo 8-hydroxy quinoline, 5-sulphonic acid reveals that it is a good chelating agent for a number of metal ions. The stability constants of metalchelates were determined in aqueous solutions. Nasanen and Ekman¹ studied the effect of ionic strength and temperature on the ionization constants of the ferron. However, no work seems to have been done on this compound in mixed solvents. As a continuation of our earlier work^{2,3} we studied the effect of temperature and dielectric constant on the ionization process of ferron in mixed solvents. The aquo-organic mixtures used were, methanol-water, ethanol-water, isopropanol-water, acetone-water, 1,4-dioxane-water, glycol-water and glycerol-water. In all our experiments we used sodium salt of ferron and have determined pK_1 for the ionization of hydroxyl group.

The substance being a sodium salt will ionize as :

Experimental

The pH titrations of the acid were conducted in a double wall jacketed glass cell through which water from a thermostat was circulated. The temperature within the cell was maintained with $\pm 0.1^\circ$. Once the solution attained the required temperature, a dilute solution of the acid of known concentration (ca. $2 \times 10^{-3} M$) was titrated with standard alkali from a calibrated 5 ml. microburette. In order to avoid dilution effect in the total volume of the solution, alkali used was much more concentrated than the acid. The pH values were noted after the addition of small increments of alkali. The ionic strength was kept constant by using a medium of 0.1M KNO_3 . Solutions were prepared in different aquo-organic mixtures using distilled water free from carbon dioxide.

The chemicals and solvents employed were all of AnalaR grade. An Elico pH meter Model L1-10 with Beckmann glass and calomel electrodes, capable of reading ± 0.02 was employed for the pH measurements. The pH meter was standardised with buffers at pH 4.00 and 9.00.

The pH values were corrected in all aquo-organic mixtures using the method of Van Uitert and Haas⁴.

pH values were noted after each addition of alkali and the corrected pH values were plotted against the volume added. It gave a sharp inflexion at one equivalent of alkali added. The ionization constant pK_1 was calculated by using Henderson's equation. Thus the obtained value of 7.05 at 35° and at ionic strength $\mu = 0.1M \text{KNO}_3$ is in good agreement with the value (7.05) in aqueous solution at 25° obtained by Nasanen and Ekman¹. Experiments were done using several aquo-organic mixtures. The calculated values of pK_1 were all within an accuracy of ± 0.02 .

Results and Discussion

The values of pK_1 so obtained in different aquo-organic mixtures at a constant ionic strength $\mu = 0.1M \text{KNO}_3$ and at 35° are presented in Table 1.

It can be seen from the table that the values of pK_1 increases with increase in the mole fraction of the organic component. The applicability of Born's equation is shown by a linear plot between $-\log {}_s\text{K}_1/w\text{K}_1$ values $1/E_s$. The values of dielectric constant (E_s) for different aquo-organic mixtures at different temperatures were taken from literature⁵. From the plots the mean radius of dianion has been calculated and presented in Table 3. The lower mean radii for acetone and isopropanol and high values in glycol and glycerol showed that the extent of solvation depends on the basicity of the solvent.

The variation of ionization constant with temperature at a constant ionic strength $\mu = 0.1M \text{KNO}_3$ was studied and the values are presented in

TABLE 1—IONIZATION CONSTANT OF FERRON (NA-SALT) IN DIFFERENT AQUO-ORGANIC MIXTURES AT 35° AND IONIC Strength $\mu = 0.1 M KNO_3$

Methanol-water		Ethanol-water		Isopropanol-water		Acetone-water		1,4-Dioxane-water		Glycol-water		Glycerol-water	
Wt%	pK ₁	Wt%	pK ₁	Wt%	pK ₁	Wt%	pK ₁	Wt%	pK ₁	Wt%	pK ₁	Wt%	pK ₁
0.00	7.05	0.00	7.05	0.00	7.05	0.00	7.05	0.00	7.05	0.00	7.05	0.00	7.05
8.08	7.12	8.07	7.14	7.98	7.22	8.03	7.25	10.28	7.24	10.97	7.04	12.26	7.06
16.33	7.20	16.31	7.25	16.30	7.44	16.33	7.50	20.51	7.50	21.70	7.09	23.97	7.08
25.32	7.28	25.10	7.43	25.00	7.70	25.32	7.82	30.73	7.85	32.24	7.14	35.10	7.13
34.53	7.45	34.50	7.60	34.60	8.16	34.53	8.35	41.00	8.25	42.50	7.23	45.63	7.15

TABLE 2—IONIZATION CONSTANT OF FERRON (NA-SALT) IN ISO COMPOSITION MIXTURES (30% V/V) AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

Temperature	Water	Methanol	Ethanol	Isopropanol	Acetone	1,4-Dioxane	Glycol	Glycerol
25°	7.22	7.49	7.61	7.90	7.93	7.96	7.09	7.05
35°	7.05	7.28	7.43	7.74	7.82	7.85	7.16	7.13
45°	6.90	7.16	7.29	7.62	7.65	7.70	7.26	7.21

Table 2. The plot of pK₁ against 1/T gave a linear relationship and the values of ΔH , ΔS and ΔG were calculated from usual thermodynamic relationship⁶ are given in Table 3. Uncertainties in the thermodynamic quantities were estimated by King's method⁷ and are $\Delta G = \pm 0.01$ Kcals mol⁻¹, $\Delta H = \pm 0.05$ KCal mol⁻¹ and $\Delta S = 0.2$ e.u.

TABLE 3—THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS OF IONIZATION CONSTANT OF FERRON (NA-SALT) IN ISO COMPOSITION MIXTURES 30% V/V

Solvent	r ₁ in Å	ΔH Kcals mole ⁻¹	ΔS e.u.	ΔG Kcals mole ⁻¹
Water	—	7.14	-9.10	9.94
Methanol	2.18	6.76	-11.40	10.26
Ethanol	2.18	6.71	-12.10	10.45
Isopropanol	1.45	5.86	-16.40	10.91
Acetone	0.84	5.72	-17.20	11.03
1,4-Dioxane	2.18	5.80	-17.10	11.07
Glycol	3.45	3.09	-22.70	10.09
Glycerol	5.26	3.51	-18.40	10.05

Based on the suggestion of Leffler and Grunwald⁸ that isokinetic relationship can also be applied to equilibrium reaction, the plot ΔH against ΔS for ionization in different solvents gave linear relationship except for glycol and glycerol. The isokinetic temperature calculated as 181°K from the present studies is much lower than the experimental temperature. Bunnett⁹ suggested that if the isokinetic temperature is well below the experimental temperature the process is controlled by ΔS . Control by ΔS is less familiar, but is often encountered in the effects of solvent on reaction rates¹⁰.

The deviation of glycol and glycerol from other solvents show that different type of mechanism occurs in these two solvents. This was confirmed by the observation that the pK₁ values in isodielectric mixture ($E_s = 62.5$) did not vary with temperature in glycol and glycerol where as there was variation in other solvents (Table 4). In isocomposition mixtures there is both electrostatic and non-electrostatic interactions, whereas in isodielectric mixtures only non-electrostatic interactions play important part.

TABLE 4—IONIZATION CONSTANT OF FERRON (NA-SALT) IN ISODIELECTRIC MIXTURES AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES. $E_s = 62.5$

Temperatures	Methanol	Ethanol	Isopropanol	Acetone	Glycol	Glycerol
25°	7.65	7.64	7.80	7.95	7.23	7.10
35°	7.35	7.35	7.43	7.72	7.23	7.15
45°	7.40	7.40	7.38	7.56	7.23	7.15

References

1. R. NASANEN and EKMAN, *Acta. Chem. Scand.*, 1952, 6, 1384.
2. P. LINGAIAH and E. V. SUNDARAM, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1971, 9, 852.
3. P. LINGAIAH, G. PUNNAIAH and E. V. SUNDARAM, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1972, 10, 521.
4. L. G. VAN UITERT and G. C. HAAS, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 451.
5. G. AKERLOF, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 54, 4125.
6. P. D. BOLTON, *J. Chem. Educ.*, 1970, 47, 633.
7. E. J. KING, *Acid Base Equilibria*, 1st Ed., Pergamon Press Ltd., Oxford, p. 191.
8. J. L. LEFFLER and E. GRUNWALD, *Rates and Equilibria of Organic Reactions*, John Wiley and Sons, New York, 1963, p. 339.
9. A. WEISSBERGER, *Techniques of Organic Chemistry*, Vol. III, Part 1, Interscience, New York, 1961, p. 207.
10. R. G. PEARSON, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1952, 20, 1478.